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DETERMINATION OF BIO ACTIVE COMPOUNDS OF A POLY HERBAL FORMULATION ACTP BY GC – MS ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The present study was designed to determine the phyto components from the chloroformic extract of a poly herbal formulation ACTP were studied. The analysis of natural products involves isolation in a pure form of plant constituents and investigation of their structure, formation, efficacy and purpose in the organism. Secondary metabolites appear to function primarily in defense against predators and pathogens and in providing reproductive advantage as intraspecific and interspecific attractant. The present study aims at quantifying the phyto constituents by chromatographic methods. Therefore, it is of interest to investigate the GC-MS analysis of the chloroformic extract of the herbal formulation ACTP were analysed Our result envisage that the presence of 21 phyto constituents of a poly herbal formulation of ACTP.

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INTRODUCTION

Natural products once served humankind as the source of all drugs, and higher plants provided most of these therapeutic agents. Today, natural products (and their derivatives and analogs) still represent over 50% of all drugs in clinical use, with higher plant-derived natural products representing 25% of the total [1]. The World Health Organization estimates that 80% of the people in developing countries of the world rely on traditional medicine for their primary health care, and about 85% of traditional medicine involves the use of plant extracts. This means that about 3.5 to 4 billion people in the world rely on plants as sources of drugs [2].

Natural products will continue to be extremely important as sources of medicinal agents. Phytochemicals, widely known as the most common antioxidants in fruits and vegetables, have been proposed as primary chemopreventive agents. Polyphenols, the major group of phytochemicals, are characterized by the presence of more than one phenol unit or building block per molecule [3]. Uncontrolled inflammation often results in chronic diseases such as arthritis, autoimmune disorders, cancer, obesity, diabetes, and neurodegenerative and vascular disease. Multiple lines of inquiry have suggested that the health benefits of phytochemicals come from their anti-oxidant effects. However, the antioxidant properties of phytochemicals can not explain all of their effects, such as specific inhibition of signal transduction and low effective dose. Numerous studies have reported that phytochemicals modulate various molecular signal transduction pathways, and research efforts have focused on the effects of phytochemicals on signaling cascades. The specific cellular and molecular targets of phytochemicals remain to be identified. After the success of tamoxifen and finasteride, which have specific molecular targets, the development of recent cancer preventive agents has been based on the discovery of precise molecular targets. Targeting several signaling pathways simultaneously using phytochemicals to achieve synergistic effects in cancer treatment has been investigated, but the efficacy of this concept for obesity or neurodegenerative diseases has not been as rigorously explored. This review focuses on recent studies of molecular targets of natural phytochemicals in cancer, obesity, and Alzheimer's disease [4]. Herbal plants have been used as a source of valuable medication in virtually all cultures worldwide due to presence of important antimicrobial principles, immune modulatory activities, and maintenance of general health, precious therapeutic properties and healing potentials; thus ensure prevention and cure for several diseases and disorders of humans and animals [5]. In India large number of plant species had been screened for their pharmacological properties but still, a vast wealth of plant species is unexplored. Medicinal plants are at interest to the field of therapeutics, as most of the drug industries depend in part of plants for the production of pharmaceutical compounds [6].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Materials

The herbal formulation *ACTP* was prepared as per available literature, in the department of Industrial Biotechnology, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research, Bharath University, Chennai, India. The equal volume of shade dried leaves of *Acalypha indica*, *Couropita guinensis*, *Tritax brogumbenz* and *Plectra amdoilicus* were taken in to marter and pistle. The plant material was coarsely powdered, then filtered by muslin cloth and the filtrate was used for further extraction.

Preparation of Plant extract

500 g of the herbal powder *ACTP* were charged in an aspiration bottle and allowed to soak in chloroform for 96 hrs at room temperature. The extract will be filtered and concentrated on a water bath. The inorganic material will be precipitated and filtered off. The filtrate will be again concentrated in a China dish and dried in vacuum. The yield of the extract will be weighed and will be stored in refrigerator for further use.

Chemicals and Reagents

All chemicals were used for this project were purchased from M/s. Sigma Chemicals, USA.

GC-MS analysis of chloroformic extract of *ACTP*

Preparation of plant extract

25gm of the powdered material of *ACTP* were soaked in 95% chloroform for 12hrs. The extract were then filtered through Whatman filter No.41 along with 2gm sodium sulfate to remove the sediments and traces of water in the filtrate. Before filtering, the filter paper was made wet with 95% ethanol along with sodium sulphate. The filtrate was then concentrated by bubbling nitrogen gas into the solution. The extract contained both polar and non-polar phyto-components in the plant material. 2 μ l of this solution was employed for GC-MS analysis. The herbal powder was extracted with chloroform and analyzed using GC-MS (GC Clarius 500 Perkin Elmer) analyzer. The data were obtained on an Elite-1(100% Dimethyl poly siloxane) column (30 0.25mm 1 μ mdf). Helium (99.999%) was used as the carrier gas with a flow rate of 1ml/min in the split mode (10:1). An aliquot of 2 μ l of ethanol solution of the sample was injected into the column with the injector temperature at 250°C. GC oven temperature started at 110°C and holding for 2min and it was raised to 200°C at the rate of 10°C/min, without holding. Holding was allowed at 280°C for 9 min with program rate of 5°C/min. The injector and detector temperatures were set at 250°C and 280°C respectively. Ion source temperature was maintained at 200°C. The mass spectrum of compounds in samples was obtained by electron ionization at 70 eV and the detector was operated in scan mode from 45-450amu (atomic mass units). A scan interval of 0.5seconds and fragments from 45 to 450 Da was maintained. The total running time was 36 minutes [7].

Identification of components

Identification was based on the molecular structure, molecular mass and calculated fragments. Interpretation on mass spectrum GC-MS was conducted using the database of National Institute Standard and Technology (NIST) having more than 62,000 patterns. The name, molecular weight and structure of the components of the test materials were ascertained. The relative percentage amount of each component was calculated by comparing its average peak area to the total areas. The spectrum of the unknown component was compared with the spectrum of the component stored in the NIST library version (2005), software, Turbomas 5.2.

Table -1 Shows the chromatogram of the active principles of Poly herbal formulation *ACTP*.

Qualitative Report

File: C:\TurboMass\DEFAULT.PRO\Data\18A-ACTP-S-2.raw
 Acquired: 18-Sep-15 05:53:40 PM
 Description:
 GC/MS Method: GC: SRU-B1.mth MS: SRU-B1 MS.EXP
 Sample ID: MMF-33MCG-ML
 Printed: 06-Oct-15 05:30 PM
 Page 1 of 2
 Vial Number: 0

#	RT	Scan	Height	Area	Area %	Norm %	Name
1	2.038	8	3,182,087,936	134,847,648.0	30.156	100.00	
2	2.599	120	14,522,305	1,915,904.6	0.428	1.42	
3	11.092	1818	9,957,749	2,306,269.8	0.516	1.71	
4	11.347	1869	14,232,965	1,876,356.8	0.420	1.39	
5	12.167	2033	36,747,596	2,951,548.0	0.660	2.19	
6	13.358	2271	25,612,764	4,240,700.0	0.948	3.14	
7	13.893	2378	53,288,892	3,865,216.8	0.864	2.87	
8	15.519	2703	43,856,688	4,930,140.0	1.103	3.66	
9	17.479	3095	86,330,776	3,773,110.8	0.844	2.80	
10	18.120	3223	179,244,992	21,585,900.0	4.827	16.01	
11	19.295	3458	128,301,440	9,030,604.0	2.020	6.70	
12	19.880	3575	44,829,624	1,595,515.0	0.357	1.18	
13	20.000	3599	247,027,360	7,804,607.0	1.745	5.79	
14	20.146	3628	128,575,624	9,244,356.0	2.067	6.86	
15	20.231	3645	102,553,736	14,938,757.0	3.341	11.08	
16	21.001	3799	79,501,768	2,458,391.5	0.550	1.82	
17	21.726	3944	46,267,676	1,595,187.6	0.357	1.18	
18	21.896	3978	12,938,542	1,442,734.4	0.323	1.07	
19	23.322	4263	54,944,844	2,100,590.2	0.470	1.56	
20	24.922	4583	90,564,520	5,360,050.0	1.199	3.97	
21	25.418	4682	750,755,648	45,610,880.0	10.200	33.82	

Inst() ACQUISITION PARAMETERS

Oven: Initial temp 50°C for 1 min, ramp 10°C/min to 290°C, hold 10 min, Inj=180°C, Volume=0 µL, Split=25:1, Carrier Gas=He,
 Solvent Delay=0.00 min, Transfer Temp=170°C, Source Temp=170°C, Scan: 50 to 500Da, Column 30.0m x 250 µm

Table -2 Shows the active principles with their retention time (RT) of Poly herbal formulation ACTP.

S.No	Retention Time	Name of the compounds
1	2.038	Trichloromethane
2	2.599	Propanoic acid ethyl ester
3	11.092	1, Undecanol
4	11.347	1,6-Cyclo decadiene,1-methyl-5-methylene-8-(1- methyl ethyl)-{5-(E-E)}
5	12.167	Caryophyllene
6	13.358	7-Hexa decane, (Z)-
7	13.893	Phenol 2,4-bis(1,1-dimethyl ethyl)-
8	15.519	1-Nonadecane
9	17.479	1- Docosene
10	18.120	Hexa decanoic acid ethyl ester
11	19.295	1- Docosene
12	19.880	(E)-9-Octadecenoic acid ethyl ester
13	20.000	9,12-Octa deca dinoic acid etyl ester
14	20.146	9,12-Octa deca dienoic acid (Z-Z)-
15	20.231	9,12-Octa deca di enoic acid (Z-Z)-
16	21.001	1-Eicosanol
17	21.726	7-Hexadecenal-(Z)-
18	21.896	9,12-Octa deca di enoic acid (Z-Z)-
19	23.322	Heptacosane
20	24.922	Heptacosane
21	25.418	Squalene

Gas chromatography has a very wide field of applications. But, its first and main area of use is in the separation and analysis of multi component mixtures such as essential oils, hydrocarbons and solvents. Intrinsically, with the use of the flame ionization detector and the electron capture detector .Gas chromatography can quantitatively determine materials present at very low concentrations. It follows, that the second most important application area is in pollution studies, forensic work and general trace analysis. Because of its simplicity, sensitivity, and effectiveness in separating components of mixtures, gas chromatography is one of the most important tools in chemistry. It is widely used for quantitative and qualitative analysis of mixtures, for the purification of compounds, and for the determination of such thermo chemical constants as heats of solution and vaporization, vapor pressure, and activity coefficients. Gas Chromatography Mass Spectroscopy, a hyphenated system which is a very compatible technique and the most commonly used technique for the identification and quantification purpose. The unknown organic compounds in a complex mixture can be determined by interpretation and also by matching the spectra with reference spectra [8].

GC-MS chromatogram of the chloroformic extract of ACTP (Fig-1) showed 28 peaks and has been identified after comparison of the mass spectra with NIST_MSMS, REPLIB and MAINLIB, indicating the presence of 21 phytochemicals. The active principles with their retention time (RT), and concentration (peak area %) are presented in Table 1. GC-MS analysis of chloroformic extract revealed the presence of 28 different compounds namely, Trichloro methane, Propanoic acid ethyl ester, 1-Undecanol, 1,6-Cyclo decadiene, 1-methyl -5-methylene-8- (1- methyl ethyl) –[5-(E-E)], Caryophyllene, 7-Hexa decane, Phenol 2,4-bis (1,1- di methyl ethyl)- , 1-Nonadecane , 1-Docosene, (E)-9-Octa decenoic acid ethyl ester, 9,12-Octa didecadienic acid ethyl ester, 9,12-Octa decadienoic acid, 9,12-Octa decadienoic acid (Z-Z)-, 1-Eicosanol , 7-Hexadecenal (z)-9,12-Octa decadienoic acid (z-z)- Heptacosane, Heptacosane, Squalene, The retention time ,and the relative percentages of the compounds present in ACTP were recorded in table 2 .The GC-MS spectrum confirmed the presence of 28 major components with the retention time 2.038, 2.599, 11.092, 11.347, 12.167, 13.358, 13.893, 15.519, 17.479, 18.120, 19.295,19.880, 20.000, 20.146 , 20.231, 21.001, 21.726, 21.896, 23.322, 24.922, 25.418, respectively (Table 2). Interpretation of mass spectrum of GC-MS was conducted using the database of National Institute Standard and Technique (NIST08s) and REPLIB having more patterns .The spectrum of the unknown component was compared with the spectrum of the known components stored in the NIST and REP library. The name of the component of the test material were determined. However, isolation of individual phytochemical constituents and subjecting it to the biological activity will definitely give fruitful results. From the results, it could be concluded that the chloroform extract of poly herbal formulation ACTP contains various bioactive compounds.

CONCLUSION

Based on our results, it is evident that the chloroform extract of a polyherbal formulation ACTP contains various bio active components and is suggested as a herbal formulation of phytopharmaceutical importance.

Source of support:

Nil

Declaration:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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